

NEW APPROACHES TO INTERACTIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6567746>

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Abstract: *the article deals with the issue of interactive learning as a new approach to the technology of the XXI century. The use of new technologies in the educational process is becoming an integral part of modern education.*

Keywords: *interactive learning, lessons, self-regulation, logical thinking.*

The technology of interactive learning is based on the phenomenon of interaction (from the English interaction - interaction, impact on each other). In the learning process, interpersonal cognitive communication and interaction of all its subjects takes place. The development of the individuality of each student and the upbringing of his personality occurs in situations of communication and interaction of people with each other.

Many major methodological innovations today are associated with the use of interactive teaching methods. Therefore, interactive learning is, first of all, interactive learning, during which the interaction between the teacher and the student is carried out.

What are the main characteristics of "interactive"? It should be recognized that interactive learning is a special form of organizing cognitive activity. She has in mind very specific and predictable goals. One of these goals is to create comfortable learning conditions, such that the student feels his success, his intellectual viability, which makes the learning process itself productive.

The essence of interactive learning is that the learning process is organized in such a way that almost all students are involved in the learning process, they have the opportunity to understand and reflect on what they know and think. The joint activity of students in the process of learning, mastering the educational material means that everyone makes their own special individual contribution, there is an exchange of knowledge, ideas, ways of activity. Moreover, this happens in an atmosphere of goodwill and mutual support, which allows not only to receive new knowledge, but also develops cognitive activity itself, transfers it to higher forms of cooperation and cooperation.

Interactive activity in the classroom involves the organization and development of dialogue communication, which leads to mutual understanding, interaction, to the joint solution of common, but significant tasks for each participant. During interactive learning, students will learn to think critically, solve complex problems based on the

analysis of circumstances and relevant information, weigh alternative opinions, make thoughtful decisions, participate in discussions, communicate with other people. To do this, individual, pair and group work is organized in the classroom, research projects, role-playing games are used, work is underway with documents and various sources of information, and creative work is used.

What are forms of interactive learning? At present, methodologists and practicing teachers have developed many forms of group work in the classroom on the modern Russian language and literature. The most famous of them are the “big circle”, “pinwheel”, “aquarium”, “brainstorming”, “debate”. These forms are effective if the class discusses any problem in general, about which students have initial ideas received earlier in the class. In addition, the topics discussed should not be very narrow. So, for example, there is no point in a group discussion of the question of what is the main idea of A.S. Pushkin's "Monument" or what members of the sentence we know. It is important that the level of the problem under discussion allows one to move from narrow philological (linguistic, literary) questions to a broad statement of the problem.

When discussing linguistic aspects, the subject of a group discussion may be, for example, currently controversial issues of morphology, syntax (in particular, parts of speech, introductory words, one-part sentences, etc.) In this case, students will jointly solve questions about the correspondence of certain other grammatical rules with new theoretical provisions in modern linguistics.

It is more appropriate to start working with 1st year students with the simplest forms of group work (“pinwheel”, “big circle”, “aquarium”). Valuable in these forms is that they allow the student not only to express their opinion, view and assessment, but also, having heard the arguments of their partner in the game, sometimes abandon their point of view or significantly change it. In the classroom for literary disciplines, this is especially true, because the questions of the history of literature, culture and art are ambiguous and require from a person not only logical thinking, but also tolerance, respect for other people's opinions.

The simplest form of group interaction is the "great circle". The work takes place in three stages.

First stage. The group sits on chairs in a large circle. The teacher formulates the problem.

Second phase. Within a certain time (approximately 10 minutes), each student individually, on his/her sheet, writes down the proposed measures to solve the problem.

Third stage. In a circle, each student reads out his proposals, the group silently listens (does not criticize) and votes on each item - whether to include it in the general decision, which is recorded on the board as the conversation progresses.

The “big circle” technique is best used in cases where it is possible to quickly determine the ways to resolve the issue or the components of this solution. With the help of this form, you can, for example, discuss the topic “Gorky and the assessment of his

work in the context of modern literary criticism ” (in the classroom for the course “History of Russian literature of the 20th century”), develop methods for conducting lessons (for the course “Methods of teaching the Russian language”).

"Aquarium" - a form of dialogue when students are invited to discuss the problem "in the face of the public." The small group chooses someone whom it can entrust to lead this or that dialogue on the problem. Sometimes it can be several applicants. All other students act as spectators. Hence the name - aquarium.

How to implement interactive communication in practice? Note that the most important condition for this is personal experience of participating in interactive training sessions . In other words, mastering active teaching methods and techniques by a teacher is simply impossible without direct inclusion in one form or another. You can read a lot of literature about active learning methods, but you can only learn them through personal participation in a game, brainstorming or discussion. We can offer several rules for the use of interactive methods:

- all participants (students) should be involved in the work to some extent. To this end, it is useful to use technologies that allow you to include all participants in the seminar in the discussion process.

- It is necessary to take care of the psychological preparation of the participants. Not all students are psychologically ready for direct involvement in certain forms of work. A well-known enslavement, stiffness, traditional behavior affects. In this regard, warm-ups, constant encouragement of students for active participation in the work, providing opportunities for their self-realization are useful.

- there should not be many students in interactive technology . The number of participants and the quality of training can be directly related. More than 30 people should not take part in the work. Only under this condition is it possible to work productively in small groups. Each student must be heard, each group must be given the opportunity to speak on the issue.

- o pay attention to the issues of procedure and regulations. It is necessary to agree on this at the very beginning and try not to violate it. For example, it is useful to agree that all participants will show tolerance for any point of view, respect the right of everyone to freedom of speech, respect for their dignity.

In conclusion, we note that interactive learning allows you to solve several problems at the same time. The main thing is that it develops communication skills, helps to establish emotional contacts between students, provides an educational task, because it teaches you to work in a team, listen to the opinion of your comrades. The use of interactive in the classroom relieves the nervous load of students and teachers, makes it possible to change the forms of their activity, switch attention to the key issues of the topic of the lesson.

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